

22NRM02 STANBC

D3: Relationship between eBC, rBC and EC

Report on the establishment of the relationship between eBC mass, rBC mass and EC mass (EN 16909:2017) based on the range of MAC values established in an intercomparison of aerosol absorption and EC mass using different monodisperse soot and aged soot aerosols (mobility diameter range 70 – 400 nm) with an uncertainty based on traceable measurements of light absorption coefficient and EC mass

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Glossary

AAE	Absorption Ångström Exponent
$b_{\text{abs}}(\lambda)$	Light absorption coefficient at wavelength λ
BC	Black carbon
eBC	Equivalent black carbon
CPMA	Centrifugal particle mass analyzer
EC	Elemental carbon
EMS	Extinction minus scattering
MAC_{BC}	Black carbon mass absorption cross-section
M_{BC}	Black carbon mass concentration
M_{eBC}	Equivalent black carbon mass concentration
M_{EC}	Elemental carbon mass concentration
M_{rBC}	Refractory black carbon mass concentration
OCU	Organic coating unit
PAX	Photoacoustic Extinctionmeter
PTAAM	Photo-thermal aerosol absorption monitor
PTI	Photo-thermal interferometry
rBC	Refractory black carbon
SMPS	Scanning mobility particle sizer
SP2	Single particle soot photometer
SSA	Single Scattering Albedo
TC	Total carbon

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1 Summary

The definition of BC is qualitative, and therefore more narrow descriptions: equivalent black carbon (eBC), refractory black carbon (rBC) and elemental carbon (EC), have been defined, corresponding to the main principles of practical BC mass measurement techniques. Among these, optical methods that yield eBC concentrations are most widely used in atmospheric studies. They require prior knowledge of the aerosol mass absorption cross section (MAC) to accurately estimate the BC mass. MAC, expressed in $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$, quantifies the ability of BC to absorb light and is essential for assessing both its climatic effects and health impacts. The MAC_{BC} of the fresh combustion aerosol is around $8 \pm 1 \text{ m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$ at 550 nm but the range is much broader for aged ambient aerosol. The aim of this deliverable is to provide information on the comparability between the different BC mass metrics across an atmospherically relevant range of aerosol MAC values, supporting more accurate evaluations of BC's climate and health impacts until a standardized reference method is established.

Monodisperse fresh and aged BC aerosol particles across a mobility diameter range 70 – 400 nm were generated using a miniCAST diffusion flame combustion generator combined with a size-selective unit and a coating unit. The soot aerosol was coated α -pinene in experiments, where aerosol SSA extended from ~ 0.03 to 0.87 and the EC/TC ratio varied in range $\sim 10 - 82\%$. The more coated (aged) particles had the highest SSA and the lowest EC/TC ratio. Aerosol absorption was measured with all reference techniques: PTAAM, EMS and PAX. They showed a good mutual correlation but for practical reasons PTAAM was selected as a campaign reference for absorption. BC aerosol mass was measured based on its refractory (rBC), elemental (EC) and optical (eBC) properties, applying two single particle soot photometers (SP2-D and SP2-XR), thermal-optical analysis (TOA) utilizing EUSAAR2 temperature protocol in two laboratories, and a multi-angle absorption photometer (MAAP) and an aethalometer (AE33). The MAC_{BC} values were determined for different aerosol types and for different instrument combinations.

The results confirmed the differences in BC mass concentrations depending on the technique of quantification, such that generally $M_{\text{rBC}} < M_{\text{EC}} < M_{\text{eBC}}$. The MAC_{rBC} for the generated aerosol varied in range 4 – 8 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-2}$ at 808 nm, which is well in line with previous studies. The relationship between M_{rBC} and M_{EC} was rather linear with a constant factor. Organic coating on soot (i.e. aerosol aging) increased the aerosol AAE systematically. However, an increase of the MAC_{BC} value following an increasing coating, as was expected based on the known aerosol lensing effect, could not be verified here. Reasons for this remain to be studied with additional data and in future experiments.

2 Introduction

2.1 Definition of eBC, rBC and EC

Black carbon (BC) is strongly light-absorbing, refractory and insoluble matter that is composed of graphite-like carbon atoms in an aggregate form. The definition of BC is qualitative and descriptive, and as such can not be quantified by any single technique alone. Therefore, for practical purposes more narrow descriptions: equivalent black carbon (eBC), refractory black carbon (rBC) and elemental carbon (EC) have been defined, closely assembling the BC but exactly corresponding to the main principles of BC mass measurement techniques (CEN/TR 18076, 2024; Petzold et al., 2013).

Mass absorption cross section (MAC) of the BC aerosol describes its' mass light-absorption ability, in units of $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$, and is an important quantity to determine the BC climatic impact. In addition, the term has been adapted to quantify the eBC mass concentration (M_{eBC}) based on measured absorption, in which case MAC is often assumed to be only a wavelength dependent constant. MAC of BC (MAC_{BC}) is thus written

$$\text{MAC}_{\text{BC}}(\lambda) = \frac{b_{\text{abs}}(\lambda)}{M_{\text{BC}}},$$

where b_{abs} is the light-absorption coefficient of the BC. In practice, BC is always replaced with one of the measurable quantities, i.e. rBC, EC or eBC.

2.2 Uncertainties in quantification of MAC_{BC}

MAC_{BC} is quantified from independent measurements of absorption and BC mass, both of which have their uncertainties. The most applied technique to measure aerosol light-absorption is filter-based absorption photometer, mainly due to its applicability for long-term monitoring with affordable price. This technique is, however, prone to several artifacts. Zanatta et al. (2016) estimated uncertainties from $\pm 15\%$ to $\pm 35\%$ for different filter-based absorption photometer instruments, but also higher discrepancies have been observed in the comparisons to less artifact prone in-situ absorption detection methods (Kalbermatter et al., 2022; Slowik et al., 2007). A reference method for carbon mass quantification based on control filter measurements is currently only available for EC (EN 16909) with an accepted method uncertainty within $\pm 10\%$ for the total carbon (TC) fraction. EC is reported as a component of TC and a long-term measurement stability within $\pm 15\%$ is generally considered acceptable (EN 16909).

The in-situ methods, such as the direct photoacoustic or photo-thermal absorption measurement techniques, or the indirect extinction-minus-scattering measurement, are alternatives to the filter-based methods. They detect aerosol absorption directly in the atmosphere but may suffer from sensitivity issues at low concentrations and are typically more complex to operate. However, they have been successfully applied in many laboratory, but also some atmospheric, studies. The in-situ methods are prominent to bring traceability in aerosol absorption measurements, following the 22NRM02 STANBC Deliverable D1: Calibration guide.

2.3 Previous intercomparisons

The fresh BC in the atmosphere has a MAC_{BC} of around $8 \pm 1 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ at 550 nm, independent of the technique of quantification (Bond and Bergstrom, 2006; Liu et al., 2020). However, this MAC_{BC} may vary depending on various changes that occur during aerosol atmospheric ageing, affecting the BC particle size, morphology and chemistry (Kalbermatter et al., 2022; Lack and Cappa, 2010; Liu et al., 2017; Romshoo et al., 2022; Yus-Díez et al., 2022), and leading to a much wider range of observed atmospheric MAC_{BC} . During the BC aerosol lifetime in the atmosphere, coating of the highly absorbing primary BC particles with non-absorbing coatings leads to a decrease in aerosol single scattering albedo (SSA), defined as the ratio of aerosol scattering-to-aerosol extinction, which further can lead to an absorption enhancement (i.e. increase of MAC_{BC}) up to a factor of about two.

Measurement of black carbon mass is highly challenging, and comparability between different methods depends not only on their internal uncertainties but is also subject to the variable properties of the BC. Therefore, it is extremely difficult to reach linearity and consistency. Pileci et al. (2021) compared co-located rBC and EC mass measurements at several European measurement sites. They found a significant systematic bias in the ratio of rBC to EC when comparing individual sites despite that the same thermal-optical protocol for EC mass analysis and the same calibration procedure for the rBC mass measurement, performed using a single particle soot photometer (SP2), were used. An overall uncertainty of the rBC-to-EC ratio was estimated as $\pm 50\%$ and suggested to be associated, among others, with the variable BC sources. The underlying causes for the variability remained unclear due to the complex cross-correlations and potential biases in the results.

Mass inter-comparisons performed using laboratory generated BC particles with more uniform properties and a well-controlled size range have led to better correlations (e.g. Corbin et al., 2020; Laborde et al., 2012b). Slowik et al. (2007) compared mass measurements of flame-generated coated and uncoated BC particles with different techniques and found that BC particle organic coating changed these instruments' response non-linearly, depending on the particle morphology and coating material thickness and refractive index. A good agreement between rBC mass measured by two techniques and eBC mass was obtained only for uncoated particles ($\pm 15\%$). Cross et al. (2010) measured a complex matrix of 318 combinations using coated and uncoated BC particles and found consistent responses from various instruments and techniques. Corbin et al. (2020) obtained a closure between BC particle mass and EC mass methods.

In StanBC we have identified the atmospherically relevant BC aerosol properties and applying these, performed a set of BC aerosol mass measurements using various techniques. The aim was to define a relationship between different operational properties of BC mass.

3 Methods

3.1 Traceable light absorption measurement

Traceability to aerosol absorption can be achieved with in-situ techniques, namely the direct photo-thermal interferometry (PTI) or photoacoustic (PA) instruments, or with the indirect differential technique, so called extinction minus scattering method (EMS).

The EMS method is based on separate measurement of aerosol extinction and scattering coefficient and the absorption coefficient is calculated as the difference between those two (Strawa et al., 2003; Virkkula et al., 2005). The EMS can be set up by separated instruments for measuring light extinction and scattering or by a combined cell for measuring light extinction and scattering simultaneously (Modini et al., 2021). The method works well for highly absorbing aerosols, but the measurement uncertainties increase strongly when the aerosol extinction is dominated by scattering particles, which is commonly encountered in the atmosphere.

Photothermal interferometry (PTI) measures aerosol absorption by employing a modulated pump beam to heat the sample by absorption of light. A second interferometric laser beam sense the change of optical path following heating of the sample. The response of PTI to a change in aerosol absorption coefficient is linear and free of scattering induced artifacts, allowing for accurate absorption measurements up to high SSA values. Several interferometer and pump beam geometries have been designed and successfully applied to measure aerosol absorption since early 1990s'. Here, a two-wavelength Photothermal Aerosol Absorption Monitor (PTAAM-2 λ), which measures the aerosol absorption coefficient at 532 and 1064 nm, was applied (Drinovec et al., 2022).

The measurement principle of the photoacoustic (PA) instruments is similar to PTI, except that the response to sample air heating is detected using an acoustic resonator. The commercially available photoacoustic extinctionsmeter (PAX, Droplet Measurement Technologies, USA) measures particle light absorption and scattering coefficient using a photo-acoustic cell and an inverse nephelometer at a wavelength of 870 nm. A good correlation between PTAAM and PAX absorption measurements was recently shown for coated soot particles (Kalbermatter et al., 2022).

Traceable calibration of EMS and PTI absorption measurements is described in 22NRM02 STANBC Deliverable D1: Calibration guide, also building on advances in 16ENV02 Black Carbon Metrology for light absorption by atmospheric aerosols -project. Traceability chain in field measurements can be obtained using a transfer standard based on photoacoustic technique, as described in 22NRM02 STANBC Deliverable D2: Traceability Chain.

3.2 BC mass measurements

Elemental carbon (EC) is defined as the fraction of total carbon, characterized by its non-volatility and chemical inertness according to the specific thermal-optical protocol. The reference method for the measurement of elemental carbon and organic carbon (OC) in ambient air is thermal-optical analysis (TOA), described in EN 16909:2017 'Ambient air - Measurement of elemental carbon (EC) and organic carbon (OC) collected on filters'. TOA relies on the thermal refractivity of EC, i.e. the fact that EC does not evolve in an inert atmosphere at temperatures below ~ 700 °C – ~ 1000 °C (Petzold et al., 2013; Schmid et al., 2001). OC is defined as the carbon fraction that evolves under a heating cycle in an inert atmosphere (e.g. helium), while the EC evolves during a subsequent heating step in an oxidising (i.e. oxygen-containing) gas mixture. The method is sensitive to various artefacts and consequently, major discrepancies in inter-laboratory comparisons of OC and EC mass have been observed (Schmid et al., 2001) . Several temperature protocols are used worldwide for TOA, which generates further heterogeneity in results. Here the analysis was proceeded with EUSAAR-2 temperature protocol.

Refractory black carbon (rBC) refers to black carbon measurements based on laser-induced incandescence (LII). In this method, refractory particles are exposed to a high-power laser beam, causing them to heat to temperatures exceeding 4000 K to emit incandescent light. The intensity of this light is directly proportional to the rBC mass. Instruments used for rBC measurement include e.g. the Single Particle Soot Photometer (SP2, Droplet Measurement Technologies, USA) and pulsed LII systems. Here we have applied SP2 which uses a

continuous high-power intra-cavity laser to achieve LII (Schwarz et al., 2006). The SP2 can detect single particles containing about 0.2 fg (50% counting efficiency) of rBC (or more) while the accuracy largely depends on the instrument calibration and the calibration material (Laborde et al., 2012b). Fullerene soot has been shown to have the characteristics most similar to ambient urban rBC (Baumgardner et al., 2012). Here the upgraded model versions SP2-D and SP2-XR were applied, which have an improved sensitivity and measurement range.

SP2 instruments are sensitive to different soot types so that their response differs between them (Moteki and Kondo, 2010; Laborde et al., 2012a). The signal response of an SP2 is also linearly proportional to the mass of BC for particles that have an rBC mass of less than ~ 15 fg. Ideally, the SP2's should be calibrated with the sample aerosol they are going to be sampling, which for atmospheric purposes is not always possible. In a laboratory setting, this approach is more feasible. Since the instrument is sensitive to the particle BC mass, an ideal calibration is done by selecting the mass of the particles e.g. using a Centrifugal Particle Mass Analyzer (CPMA) or Aerosol Particle Mass Analyser (APM). The uncertainty (reproducibility) of rBC calibrations for the SP2 has been shown to be about 10% (Laborde et al., 2012b).

In field measurements, black carbon mass is typically determined optically using filter-based absorption photometers. They rely on a calculation of aerosol light absorption coefficient and a constant MAC_{eBC} , either pre-set by the instrument or provided by the user, needs to be applied. While filter-based photometers are prone to several complex artifacts, their undisputable benefit is their suitability for long-term monitoring at a wide concentration range (Asmi et al., 2021). Here a standard seven wavelength filter absorption photometer model AE33 (Aerosol d.o.o, Slovenia) (Drinovec et al., 2022; Yus-Díez et al., 2021) and a standard single wavelength multi-angle mass absorption photometer model 5012 (MAAP, Thermo Scientific, USA) (Petzold and Schönlinner, 2004) were applied for eBC measurements.

3.3 Generation of monodisperse soot and aged soot aerosols

Monodisperse fresh and aged BC aerosol particles across a mobility diameter range 70 – 400 nm were generated using a miniCAST diffusion flame combustion generator combined with a size-selective unit and a coating unit. The complete BC aerosol generator setup is shown in Figure 1 and consisted of a MiniCAST Model 5203C BC generator, operating at a propane flow rate of 90 ml min^{-1} , oxidation air flow rate of 2.5 l min^{-1} , dilution air flow rate of 20 l min^{-1} and quench gas flow rate of 20 l min^{-1} . To prevent early coagulation, the aerosol was diluted with a flow rate of 50 l min^{-1} . An optional coagulation section allowed the particles to coagulate under controlled conditions. An additional diluter provided a stable volume flow and stopped unwanted further coagulation. The subsequent catalytic stripper removed organic components to ensure BC particles with high elemental-to-total carbon (EC/TC) -ratio. In this configuration an EC/TC ratio of $>80\%$ was achieved. Using a centrifugal particle mass analyzer (CPMA, Cambustion Ltd, UK) and a scanning mobility particle sizer (SMPS), a mass mobility exponent (McMurry et al., 2002) of approximately 2.25 to 2.28 was determined, indicating that the particles had a fractal structure with a low fractal dimension of approximately 1.8 over a size range from 40 to 400 nm mobility diameter (c.f. Figure 2).

Figure 1: BC aerosol generator setup for complete aerosol production and modification consisted of a miniCAST soot generator, optional coagulation line for size modification, 1st dilution section, catalytic stripper, optional monodisperse size selection section using Aerodynamic Aerosol Classifier (AAC), organic coating unit (OCU) for aerosol aging and a 2nd dilution section.

Figure 2: Mass mobility exponents with and without the coagulation line for uncoated soot particles.

An OCU (organic coating unit) was used to coat the soot particles with α -pinene. By controlling the α -pinene flow, the saturation of the α -pinene in the reaction chamber could be adjusted to produce coatings of different thicknesses. Furthermore, exposure to UV light causes the particles to age through photo-oxidation. The resulting BC volume size distributions are shown in Figure 3. The volume size distributions are shown for three soot core sizes with volume mean diameters of 84, 116 and 305 nm and varying coating thicknesses. The single scattering albedo (SSA=ratio of light scattering to light extinction) and particle total volume are correspondingly increasing with the increasing coating. This leads to an increase in the particle mean mobility diameter, with an exception seen for 305 nm core size, where after the first stage of coating the particle mobility diameter decreases likely due to morphology effects and particle restructuring.

A)

B)

C)

Figure 3: Volume size distribution for soot cores with mean volume diameters of A) 84 nm, B) 116 nm and C) 305 nm. Increasing single scattering albedo (SSA) indicates an increase of particle organic (α -pinene) coating.

3.4 Intercomparison of aerosol absorption and BC mass using different monodisperse soot and aged soot aerosols

For the intercomparison of the different BC mass measurement techniques on the range of atmospherically relevant MAC values and BC core sizes, three soot core sizes (volume mean mobility diameter 84, 116 and 305 nm) in aging range across no coating (SSA \sim 0.1) to thick coating (SSA up to 0.85) were generated. Aerosol light absorption was measured by EMS, PTAAM and PAX techniques. The wavelength range was from 450 to 870 nm. From this set of primary and secondary absorption measurement techniques, a *campaign reference* was chosen to facilitate data evaluation. Mass concentrations of soot were measured using a thermographic technique giving elemental carbon EC, with a single particle soot photometers (SP2) giving rBC and with filter absorption photometers providing eBC. eBC was calculated applying the instrument internally pre-set MAC_{eBC} values of $6.6 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and $10.35 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for MAAP and AE33, respectively, at wavelengths 637 nm and 660 nm.

4 Results

4.1 Intercomparison of reference instruments for light absorption coefficients

A comparison of the light absorption coefficients was made for the two reference measurement techniques EMS and PTAAM, and they were found in good agreement. Since EMS has higher uncertainties at high single scattering albedos and low BC concentrations, PTAAM was chosen as the campaign reference.

For comparison, values from the PTAAM were inter- or extrapolated to the wavelength of the EMS using the absorption Ångström exponent defined by

$$AAE = - \frac{\ln(b_{abs}(450\text{ nm})/b_{abs}(808\text{ nm}))}{\ln(450\text{ nm}/808\text{ nm})} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

Figure 4 shows the results for all the soot generated during the laboratory intercomparison campaign.

The combined uncertainty (k=2) of PTAAM was determined to be 8.4% and 12.4% for 450 and 808 nm respectively (22NRM02 STANBC Deliverable D1: Calibration guide). The uncertainty depends on the method of calibration. Here the values for calibrating with NO₂ at 450 nm and with NO₂ + Nigrosine at 808 nm were taken. In case that inter- or extrapolation of wavelength is required, additional uncertainty is inserted. The uncertainty for EMS strongly depends on single scattering albedo and the height of the light absorption coefficient. The uncertainties are discussed in and the values for the combined uncertainty (k=2) are tabulated in 22NRM02 STANBC Deliverable D2: Traceability Chain.

A)

B)

C)

Figure 4: Absorption coefficient measured with EMS compared to PTAAM. If necessary, the absorption coefficients measured by PTAAM at 450 and 807 nm were inter- or extrapolated to the wavelength of EMS. PTAAM was compared to EMS at A) 450 nm, B) 525 nm and C) 635 nm, and a linear regression was fitted. The data labels next to the points indicate the aerosol single scattering albedos.

4.2 Relationship between eBC mass, rBC mass and EC mass (EN 16909:2017)

The rBC mass size distribution was measured by a SP2-D for the three core BC particle sizes added with varying amount of coating. The mass mean diameter of the rBC size distribution did not change significantly as a function of varying coatings (Figure 5). A reduced detection efficiency for smaller particles is evident, indicated by the dashed line in Figure 5. By fitting a log-normal size distribution, the total mass loss due to the SP2 lower detection limit was estimated. The losses were calculated to be less than 5% and 3% for the 84 and the 116 nm core sizes, respectively. For the core sizes larger than 305 nm it was not possible to reliably define a range of reduced detection efficiency. Furthermore, it is not clear why the SP2 lower detection limit was different for 84 and 116 nm core sizes. Therefore, the data have not been corrected for loss of mass below the lower detection limit until a satisfactory explanation can be found.

A)

B)

C)

Figure 5: rBC mass size distributions measured with SP2-D for the core sizes A) 84 nm, B) 116 nm and C) 305 nm. For each core size, three to four varying coatings, indicated by the different single scattering albedo (SSA), were generated.

The rBC mass concentration was also measured using an extended range SP2-XR. The settings for this instrument were not optimised for the high concentration. However, the data are presented here for completeness. A scatter plot of rBC (using both SP2-D and SP2-XR) with EC shows a good correlation between the SP2-D and the thermographic method, with approximately 15% lower values for rBC from the SP2 and an additional offset (Figure 6). The differences in slope can be explained by the different calibration methods and different definitions of rBC and EC. The reasons for the offset remain unclear. The values for EC were obtained from the off-line analysis carried out at METAS. For reproducibility, an independent analysis following EN 16909:2017 at NPL and METAS was performed. The average ratio between the values resulted in 0.93, with 83% of the ratios being between 0.75 and 1.25. However, since the punched-out area for the samples at NPL was not optimal due to the small sample size, only the values of the measurement at METAS are used in the following.

Figure 6: Correlation between rBC from SP2-D and SP2-XR versus EC.

The eBC mass concentration (M_{eBC}) determined by MAAP and AE33 requires an instrument internal pre-set MAC_{eBC} value. Since these have been determined independently for different types of carbon black, the M_{eBC} values differ from each other's and also from the elemental carbon mass concentration (M_{EC}) obtained in this campaign. Therefore, the eBC mass concentrations as provided "default" from the instruments are plotted without any corrections in Figure 7. We have not included error information for the individual measuring points here, as our sole aim is to highlight the difference between the measured eBC and EC mass concentration. It can be seen that the M_{eBC} values from MAAP are closer to the M_{EC} values than those from the AE33.

Figure 7: Equivalent black carbon (eBC) mass concentration from MAAP (637 nm, red line) and from AE33 (660 nm, blue line) versus elemental carbon (EC) mass concentration.

4.3 MAC values derived from an intercomparison of aerosol absorption and BC mass

We derived the MAC_{BC} values based on reference absorption measurement and the BC mass measured with three independent techniques. Based on the results above, we can roughly estimate that for the aerosol generated here applies $M_{rBC} < M_{EC} < M_{eBC}$. A calculation applying rBC mass concentration as a proxy for BC mass will thus lead to an upper limit estimate of MAC_{BC} .

The combined measurements of the mass absorption coefficient MAC_{rBC} with characteristic aerosol properties are detailed in Table 1 and further plotted in Figure 8, demonstrating the derived MAC_{rBC} values for the three soot core sizes of 80, 120 and 180 nm for different degrees of coating and the corresponding AAE as a measure of the wavelength dependence of light absorption. The AAE increases with increasing coating for all core sizes. In contrast, MAC does not show systematic behaviour with increasing coating and either an increase or a decrease of MAC value can be observed. Overall, the longer 808 nm wavelength, in comparison to the shorter 450 nm wavelength, seems less sensitive to changes in MAC as a function of the coating.

MAE_{EC} values are not shown here because the MAC values for rBC and EC essentially change by a relatively constant factor (see Figure 6).

Figure 8: A-C) MAC_{rBC} values obtained using the absorption coefficients from PTAAM at wavelengths 450 nm (blue line= and 808 nm (red line) and the rBC mass concentration from SP2-D as a function of SSA for different soot core mean mobility diameters, and D-F) the derived AAE values for the same experiments.

Table 1: Detailed list of parameters associated with the measurement of the MAC values characterising the bare soot and coated aerosol number and volume mobility size, aerosol EC/TC ratio, single scattering albedo (SSA) and the mean mass.

Number mean mobility diameter [nm] of size-selected soot cores	Volume mean mobility diameter [nm] of coated particles	EC/TC Ratio [%]	SSA [-]	rBC mean mass [fg]
80	84	66	0.05	0.22
80	123.4	19	0.29	0.21
80	183.3	12	0.72	0.21
120	116.5	82	0.03	0.5
120	123.7	36	0.18	0.5
120	179.9	19	0.66	0.5
120	220.2	10	0.87	0.58
180	305.9	37	0.12	2.88
180	239.7	29	0.51	2.87
180	280.1	19	0.78	2.72
180	323.9	13	0.87	2.80

4.4 Uncertainty based on traceable measurements of light absorption coefficient and EC mass

The uncertainties in absorption and BC mass measurements were discussed in sections 4.1 and 4.2, respectively. Here we give only a short summary of the combined uncertainties.

The uncertainties of the MAC result from the uncertainty of the absorption coefficient and the uncertainties of the determining rBC or EC masses, respectively. The uncertainties of the individual components and the combined uncertainties are summarised in Table 2. The uncertainties in measured absorption were determined in this project, and are fully explained in 22NRM02 STANBC Deliverable D1: Calibration guide. The uncertainties in rBC were taken from the literature, where 10% uncertainty was calculated (type A only). Systematic evaluation of rBC method uncertainties for both A- and B-type sources is required. Combined uncertainties in EC are based on sampling related uncertainties (such as positive/negative artifacts on the filters and filter loading variability), calibration/instrumental variability and thermo-optical analysis issues (e.g. charring effect, laser stability and temperature ramp accuracy). The EC uncertainty tends to be lower for medium to high EC concentrations and increases significantly for lower concentrations due to detection limit challenges and higher noise to signal ratios. In an inter-laboratory comparison of 17 laboratories, repeatability for EC applying EUSAAR2 protocol of 15% was obtained (Panteliadis et al., 2015).

Table 2: Uncertainty for the single components of MAC and combined uncertainties.

Component	$b_{\text{abs}} (450 - 808 \text{ nm})$	rBC	EC	MAC_{rBC}	MAC_{EC}
Uncertainty (k=2)	8.4% – 12.4 %	10%	15%	13% – 16%	17% – 20%

5 Conclusions

Measurements of the light absorption coefficient using independent methods have shown that the light absorption can be consistently derived at several wavelengths. In contrast, the determination of rBC and EC masses shows systematic differences that have already been described in the literature. Overall, a mass absorption cross section (MAC) and associated uncertainties can be determined.

The measurements showed that an alpha-pinene organic coating on soot cores caused a strong change in the aerosol single scattering albedo. However, an increased coating and single scattering albedo did not cause a strong absorption enhancement as expected through the known lensing effect by the non-absorbing coating. Mie modelling suggest that the lensing effect in our experiment would be in range 1.1 – 1.9, but this magnitude was not observed in the measurements. It was found that light absorption increased more at short wavelengths (450 nm) compared to long wavelengths (808 nm). Similar results were reported by Kalbermatter et al. (2022). As the coating did not result in the expected increase in MAC, mechanisms to explain this behaviour were discussed. One possibility is that, due to the boundary conditions, alpha-pinene may have adhered to the particle not only by condensation but also by nucleation-coagulation processes, possibly resulting in mixed particles with a different morphology than expected, and thus no lensing effect could develop. Data from additional instruments are being analysed to clarify this issue together with the light scattering calculations.

6 References

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